

AI DIRECT TRANSLATION, NOT SO MUCH... ONE MORE STEP

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While translators have traditionally been an invisible force, relegated to preserving rather than shaping texts, the rise of artificial intelligence (AI) translation has reshaped the translation landscape, rendering translators visible. AI translation mechanisms are trained on primarily English language Western writing, and therefore preserve this influence in their translations.

While translating, AI preserves Anglo-American cultural phrases, even when L1 and L2 are not English. Consequently, the "task of the translator" to add, what Lawrence Venuti refers to as "local flavor", becomes necessary and visible. As AI translates in a standardized manner that reflects Anglo-American culture, translators, as Michael Cronin predicts, become cultural envoys that preserve the aura of a text rather than simply replicating an item from L1 to L2.

As translators intervene in the creation of the target text, they create a second tier in the process of either providing AI with cultural training, or reediting AI output. In this way, AI translation becomes an indirect task that highlights the role of cultural expertise in human communication. Rather than a divinely inspired work, translation becomes material labour. The translator is now tasked with adding nuance and locality to an AI translation that lacks a creative element and cultural sensitivity. This allows the translator to be recognized as an active creator rather than a vessel.